

SECTION OF BIOLOGICAL AND MEDICAL SCIENCES

SPECIFIC DEVELOPMENTAL DISORDERS OF SPEECH AND LANGUAGE

Aliyev R.

5th year student

Tbilisi State Medical University

Tbilisi, Georgia

<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-5536-6696>

Abstract

Speech delay is a delay in the acquisition of verbal language in children compared to the age norm. Speech delay is characterized by a qualitative and quantitative underdevelopment of vocabulary, an underdeveloped expressive speech, and the absence of phrasal speech by age 2 and coherent speech by age 3. Specific speech and language development disorders are persistent difficulties in developing oral and/or written language that occur in children with normal hearing, intelligence, and articulatory abilities. They manifest themselves in delayed speech onset, a limited vocabulary, and grammatical errors (alalia, general speech underdevelopment). Disorders in which the normal acquisition of language skills is impaired early in development. These conditions are not directly related to neurological or speech impairments, sensory impairments, intellectual disability, or environmental factors. Specific speech and language disorders are often accompanied by related problems, such as difficulties with reading, spelling, and pronunciation, interpersonal dysfunction, and emotional and behavioral disorders.

Keywords: specificity, disorder, development, speech, language, late, speaking, writing, words, acquiring, difficulties, diagnostics, reading, speed, neurology, speech therapy, psychology.

INTRODUCTION AND PURPOSE:

Typically, all specific speech development disorders begin to manifest in childhood. The child uses sounds below the level appropriate for their mental age, but still has a normal level of speech skills. At the same time, the child has normal hearing, adequate mental development, a properly developed articulatory apparatus, and normal language skills. At the same time, children begin to speak late (their first words may not appear until age 2). Lexical language development deficits develop (they learn words poorly), and difficulty comprehending long sentences (especially at a fast pace) manifests itself, so children themselves often express themselves in short sentences. Reading and writing difficulties occur during school preparation. The main causes of the manifestation of symptoms in the so-called risk group can be pre-natal causes, birth trauma, hyperactive children, behavioral disorders, and frequently ill children. The goals of studying the medical and psychological aspects of speech delays in children are aimed at early identification of causes, a comprehensive assessment of higher mental functions, the development of individualized intervention programs, and the prevention of persistent developmental disorders. This allows for the integration of medical interventions (neurology) with psychological interventions (development of speech, attention, and memory).

METHOD: Literature analysis, personal observations and comparative analysis were used in the study.

RESEARCH:

This condition may be associated with dysfunctions of multiple organ systems, particularly the central nervous system (CNS) and the orofacial musculature. A correct diagnosis usually requires multidisciplinary

approach such as a neurologist, logopedist, psychologist, and osteopath. Typically, such patients are referred to an osteopath after comprehensive clinical evaluation. If necessary, the doctor will prescribe instrumental and laboratory diagnostic investigations, including neuroimaging and neurological assessment. The primary clinical manifestations include delayed speech and language development (speech delay) and articulatory disorders, characterized by distorted or substituted phonemes. According to statistics, the prevalence of the disorder is approximately 10% among children under 8 years of age and approximately 5% among those over 8 years of age, with boys being affected 2-3 times more often than girls [2;4;6;11].

Prenatal etiologies include genetic abnormalities, intrauterine infections, chronic maternal diseases, micronutrient deficiencies, psychosocial stress, and exposure to environmental toxins. They operate from conception until parturition, affecting fetal neurodevelopment. The main factors are maternal age, lack of preconception care, obesity, and gestational or chronic hypertension. Speech disorders associated with perinatal and birth trauma are frequently linked to perinatal hypoxia-ischemia, traumatic brain injury, or cranial nerve compression, resulting in neurodevelopmental delay, paresis of the articulatory muscles, and functional impairment of cortical speech centers, including Broca's and Wernicke's areas.

FINDINGS:

The main symptoms include delayed speech and language development, dysarthric (slurred) articulation, impaired attention and concentration, and emotional lability. Early therapeutic intervention (from age 2) helps compensate for these impairments. Speech disorders associated with hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) in children are caused by accelerated

cognitive processing and attention deficits, manifesting as tachylalia (accelerated speech), impulsive or explosive speech, and breathing and articulation problems. Developmental delays, slurring, and syllable omission are also common, as are difficulties in verbal formulation and pragmatic communication. Speech impairments in behavioral disorders often manifest as dysarthria (impaired articulation and intonation), aphasia (difficulty understanding/producing speech), and echolalia (automatic repetition). Characteristics include monotonic prosody, flattened affect, learning difficulties, impulsivity, and deficits in social interaction. Frequent illnesses (especially viral infections and acute respiratory viral infections) in children weaken the body, leading to delayed speech ontogenesis (dysphonia, a weak, hoarse voice) and delayed development of all speech components. Constant oral breathing secondary to adenoid hypertrophy often causes speech impediments. Consultation with a pediatric ENT specialist and speech therapist is required [3;7;9;11].

A diagnosis of speech delay is usually given to children under 5-6 years of age, when there is hope for the natural development of the systems that slow the maturation of the psyche and speech function. The delay can manifest as delayed speech development, partial speech loss, or complete speech absence. This article discusses the main causes, signs, and types of speech delays in children. Speech delays associated with functional disorders arise from unfavorable upbringing conditions (pedagogical neglect) and severe somatic illnesses that impede the child's normal socialization and education, but are not associated with a disorder of the central nervous system. Often, these problems are caused not so much by anatomical factors as by psychological and social factors.

Speech development delay of organic etiology results from structural damage to the central nervous system (CNS). This can result from impaired functioning of partially damaged neural structures or functionally interconnected cortical and subcortical regions, i.e., from brain injury. There are two types of such delays:

Alalia. A complete or partial absence of speech with normal hearing and intellectual development. The child understands speech but does not speak or uses a limited set of words. This is due to organic damage to the speech areas of the brain, which makes it difficult to develop or understand speech.

Dysarthria. Problems with pronouncing sounds due to insufficient innervation (nerve conduction) of the muscles involved in speech, such as the tongue and lips. The child may have unclear, slurred speech and difficulty pronouncing sounds that require fine coordination. This occurs with damage to the central nervous system.

During the first consultation, an osteopathic physician looks for the cause of the disorder in the body, performing a visual examination and special manual tests [7;10].

Biological causes of speech delays: central nervous system pathologies such as cerebral palsy, brain injuries, encephalitis, and other injuries sustained in infancy and early childhood-that affect the motor skills necessary for pronouncing sounds and phrases. Hearing

or vision impairments. Difficulties in perceiving and processing speech can cause delays. Mental retardation. Children with mental retardation have difficulty acquiring and applying speech skills. Severe somatic illnesses that interfere with normal socialization and education, but are not related to a disorder of the central nervous system: for example, severe heart defects-the child is prohibited from any physical activity and attending children's educational institutions, which severely limits their social circle [9;11].

Birth injuries, prematurity, and infections acquired during the prenatal period. Psychological etiologies: unfavorable psychological environment in the family-speech problems in a child can arise due to stress and anxiety. Lack of interaction with peers. Lack of adequate verbal stimulation from adults. Isolation and associated social deprivation (unmet need for communication). **Socioeconomic factors** also play a significant role. Children from disadvantaged families may have limited access to education, which can lead to delayed speech development. It is important to note that the causes of delayed speech development in children can be complex and involve several factors.

Speech developmental impairments restrict the child's interactions with peers and adults. This can lead to communication anxiety, avoidant behavior, and impaired socialization, so it is important to begin psychotherapeutic interventions as early as possible. The physician identifies the problem, functional restrictions, such as hypomobility and restricted range of motion in the musculoskeletal system, including joints. There can be many causes. People with identical symptoms may have completely different problems. Each osteopathic technique is individually tailored, depending on the patient's age, somatic characteristics, and specific functional impairments. Osteopathic techniques involve articulation work with the articular apparatus (joint work). These techniques primarily involve myofascial release (working with the fascia-the connective tissue covering the muscles-using the physician's hand movements, which leads to tissue relaxation), followed by muscle-energy techniques (the patient is asked to move and rotate according to the physician's prescribed algorithm). These improve regional blood circulation, enhance oxygen and nutrient delivery, facilitate metabolic waste removal, and normalize tissue biomechanics. One osteopathic session lasts from 30 minutes to an hour, and is performed every 10-14 days. The number of sessions is determined individually with the doctor; on average, 5-10 procedures with varying frequency are sufficient [4;5].

Regular preventive examinations with a pediatrician will help in early detection of potential risks of speech development disorders. Equally important is a critical assessment by parents or caregivers regarding speech development disorders. It is especially important to promptly identify and begin treatment for persistent auditory impairments (for example, those resulting from otitis media with effusion) before they negatively impact speech development. Speech development, an integral part of a child's overall development, will only benefit from active and attentive parental attention. Adults unconsciously adapt to the child's

needs and structure their speech with short, simple sentences, repeating or emphasizing important information several times [5;9].

The causes of speech development disorders, such as auditory impairments, should be addressed as quickly as possible. Speech development therapy is conducted individually, often through corrective and therapeutic exercises, which are most often performed by speech therapists. When speech disorders coexist with other neurodevelopmental or developmental impairments, an integrated, multidisciplinary intervention strategy is required [6;10].

It is crucial to promptly implement the treatment and preventative measures recommended by the pediatric clinic. Currently, there are many pharmacological agents available that promote the accelerated maturation of certain brain structures and normalize existing pathological processes. Nevertheless, speech therapists are essential for children's speech development.

RESULTS:

Today, we are witnessing the active implementation of innovative medical and psychological approaches to the correction of speech disorders in early childhood. One of the most promising directions is the application of information and communication technologies (ICT), including specialized software platforms and educational gaming applications, designed to automate articulatory patterns, enhance phonemic awareness, and facilitate the development of lexical and grammatical competencies. Telemedicine, providing access to speech therapy through remote consultations and sessions, is also becoming widespread. The bioacoustic correction method is an innovative approach based on the use of acoustic stimuli modulated according to individual electroencephalogram parameters, with the aim of normalizing the functional state of the brain and optimizing speech processes. Thus, early speech therapy intervention is an effective and essential means of preventing and correcting speech disorders in young children. The use of modern diagnostic and intervention methods based on the principles of integrative and activity-based approaches, as well as the active involvement of families in the intervention process, enables significant results and ensures the full development of each child. Speech therapists play a central role in the early intervention system, providing diagnostic, interventional, consulting, educational, and scientific and methodological support. Investments in early intervention are investments in the future of each child and society as a whole.

In modern speech therapy practice, a wide range of methods and techniques are used to correct speech disorders in young children, designed to optimize speech apparatus function and develop speech competencies. Traditional and widely used methods include: articulatory exercises, aimed at developing the mobility

and coordination of the muscles of the articulatory apparatus; speech therapy massage, which improves muscle tone and circulation in this area; exercises for developing phonemic hearing, which promote the ability to distinguish and analyze speech sounds; techniques for developing the lexical and grammatical structure of speech, including games and exercises to enrich vocabulary and master grammar; and sensory integration methods, which stimulate and harmonize the interaction of the visual, auditory, tactile, and proprioceptive systems.

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